

TOUCHLESS CONFINEMENT OF HISTORICAL MASONRY COLUMNS WITH FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMER SHEETS

Francesco Micelli, University of Salento, ITALY, francesco.micelli@unisalento.it
Alessio Cascardi, University of Calabria, ITALY, alessio.cascardi @unisalento.it
Maria Antonietta Aiello, University of Salento, ITALY, antonietta.aiello @unisalento.it

ABSTRACT

FRP-confinement is one of the quickest and effective techniques in order to preserve the structural integrity of historical masonry columns after damage due to seismic events or cracking due to overloads. In this scenario, the present research focused on new touch-less confinement techniques in which the FRP can be easily removed. An experimental program was run, by testing half-scale masonry columns with square cross-section under compression loads, confined with carbon-FRP. Unconfined columns were tested as control series, then FRP-confined columns with traditional wet lay-up were tested in addition to touch-less FRP-confined columns. Results confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed techniques, at different levels. The full removability of the FRP sheets was evidenced by removing the jacket when the compression tests ended.

KEYWORDS

Masonry; Columns; Confinement; Reversibility; Heritage;

INTRODUCTION

State of the art

Most of the artefacts of the cultural heritage found in different parts of the world are masonry constructions, and many of these have been accredited as UNESCO sites also in seismic areas such as Italy. Such structures have manifested over the centuries structural vulnerabilities as well as problems of instability also related to seismic events, degradation of materials, subsequent modifications, load increases, etc. This scenario makes the protection and retrofitting of heritage construction a central issue in today's structural engineering, especially after those seismic events that severely damage the existing structures. For those buildings that fall within the cultural heritage because of particular architectural beauty or historical importance, the conservation of existing masonry buildings requires strengthening techniques that are minimally invasive and ensure reversibility and compatibility with the substrate in order to achieve a sustainable intervention from both mechanical and architectural perspectives. As indicated among the Principles of the ICOMOS (International Council for Monuments and Sites) Charter, drafted by the ISCARSAH (International Scientific Committee on the Analysis and Restoration of Structures of Architectural Heritage) committee, the choice between "traditional" and "innovative" intervention techniques must be evaluated on a case-by-case basis, giving preference to those that are less invasive and more compatible with the materials and historical values of the building. Moreover, it is preferable that interventions be reversible, so that they can eventually be removed and replaced, without leaving traces, with alternative measures deemed more appropriate in the future in light of new knowledge (ISCARSAH, 2003). From this perspective, the use of FRP as Externally Bonded Reinforcement (EBR) for heritage masonry structures is often strongly discouraged because the removability of the intervention is not assured by the use of polymer adhesives, bonded to the fibers and to the masonry substrate. Thus the traditional wet lay-up technique does not allow preserving the substrate because of the chemical bonding. The case of masonry columns with frescos is the most suggestive in this field. However, in the case of column confinement, although a complete bond can be easily developed between the substrate and the FRP by the adhesive and primer application, this is not strictly necessary for the mechanical effectiveness of confinement. In fact, lateral pressure is applied by the FRP as a result of transverse expansion of the column, regardless of the presence of a strong bond. At the moment different early (Aiello et al.,

2009) and recent studies (Minafò et al., 2017; Alotaibi et al., 2022; Napoli et al., 2022; Narayanan et al., 2023) confirmed the high effectiveness of external FRP-confinement for masonry columns in terms of load bearing and deformation capacity. Also active confinement has been experienced by activating shape memory alloys inside the composite sheets in order to increase the stiffness under service loads (Micelli et al., 2014). Also in this case the improvements of FRP-confinement were fully exploited in both Serviceability Limit State (SLS) and Ultimate Limit State (ULS). The latest research trends in the field of reinforcing masonry construction have led to the study and use of fiber-reinforced materials with an inorganic matrix, based on cement or lime mortar, to avoid a strong discrepancy between the high properties of reinforcement (carbon fibres stronger than steel i.e.) and the poorer properties of masonry, as well as to facilitate installation and make the outer reinforcement layer permeable to moisture cycles. With reference to these new market trends, recent studies (Estevan et al., 2020) show that the use of FRCM (Fabric Reinforced Cementitious Matrix) materials with inorganic matrix can also be successfully employed with in the field of external confinement of masonry columns. Compared to FRPs, the mechanical increase achieved appear smaller, yet still significant for design purposes. In these cases, differences were found with respect to the case of FRPs with regard to the influence of the matrix properties (Micelli et al. 2020), which influences the distribution of confinement stresses due to the progressive decay of stiffness caused by the progressive cracking during the loading phases. Only a preliminary research conducted by the authors (Cascardi et al. 2019) on small scale specimens addressed the problem of reversibility in the field of external FRP-confinement of masonry column.

Research significance

Due to the encouraging results of the first stages that demonstrated a confinement effectiveness up to 218% in small scale masonry, the present research illustrate the experimental results obtained on half-scale masonry columns, using the two techniques that evidenced the best performances among those preliminarily investigated, in terms of strength increase and reversibility. The first consists in the application on the masonry surface of an adhesion-inhibiting primer (Liquid Adhesion Inhibitor or LAI) and compatible with the breathability of the substrate, so as to separate the latter from the FRP matrix. The second consists in the interposition of a Mylar™ film between the column and the FRP jacket. In both cases, a tape of unidirectional carbon fibers (C-FRP) was used for jacketing the columns. The proposed techniques were applied both on columns made of limestone blocks and natural tuff blocks, bonded by hydraulic mortar simulating the historical construction techniques. Two stones of high porosity were purposely chosen in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the techniques. The columns were subjected to axial compression test. The effectiveness of confinement was evaluated by comparing the compressive strength and deformability of the reinforced columns with those obtained for unconfined specimens. Whereas, the reversibility of each confinement technique was verified by comparing the substrate before confinement with CFRP and after testing also in relation to the case of confinement applied by the wet lay-up technique.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

The experimental study involved a total of sixteen specimens in the form of half-scale masonry columns and evaluated the effectiveness and degree of reversibility of confinement with CFRP, varying both the substrate material and the reinforcement application technique. In all cases, the columns were fully wrapped by means of single layer of uni-directional carbon fiber sheet. Specifically, eight specimens were made of natural tuff blocks (here referred to as "NAP") and the other 8 of limestone blocks (here referred to as "PL").

Proposed reversible strengthening techniques

In order to achieve the goal of reversibility two distinct techniques were tested, having a different methodological approach: Interposition of a Separating Film (ISF); Liquid Adhesion Inhibitor (LAI). The ISF technique consists of introducing a polymer film on the column, before the laying of the primer and impregnation of the fibres, thus the FRP jacket is cured without touching the surface of the column. This prevents the thermosetting matrix from impregnating the substrate, thereby compromising the irreversible permanent bond. This approach lends itself well to applications in confinement interventions, since the effectiveness of the mechanism depends on contact, not bonding

to the substrate. In this case the polymer film should have adequate characteristics to achieve a successful application, including: chemical inertia with the resin; negligible roughness in order to facilitate possible future removal; flexibility (i.e., low stiffness) to make installation quick and easy; resistance to the heat produced by the exothermic cross-linking reaction of the epoxy matrix; low cost so as not to further increase the cost of the operations. The choice fell on using a Mylar™ film with a thickness of 0.03 mm, almost negligible surface roughness and non-adhesive properties.

The second proposed technique, instead of placing a physical barrier between the reinforcement and the substrate, uses a chemical decoupling agent, to be spread in liquid form on the column surface. The goal is to create a protective, transparent layer by using an adhesion-inhibiting liquid that prevents bonding between the FRP system (resin + primer) and the masonry. A liquid release agent was already investigated in Cascardi et al. (2019), which was observed to assure detachment properties and absence of physical and chromatic alteration of the substrate at the same time. The liquid used is composed of: two parts of a water-repellent impregnating agent based on silanes and siloxanes in an aqueous emulsion; one part of PVA (PolyVinyl Alcohol) pellicular release agent in aqueous solution. The use of the above materials is due to the fact that chemical adhesion, when epoxy resin is used, is developed by hydrogen bonds, to prevent which, the liquid release agents used must precisely possess water-repellent characteristics. In addition, these materials are also used to protect the masonry substrate from weathering.

Specimens preparation

Within the group of eight specimens of the NAP series (tuff masonry), two of them were strengthened by using the "traditional" manual wet lay-up technique, without any concern about the reversibility of the jacketing process. These specimens are labeled as "NAP-FRP-01" and "NAP-FRP-02"; two were first coated with a Mylar™ thin sheet (0.03 mm), according to the ISF technique, and afterwards they were fully wrapped by using CFRP unidirectional sheets, for them the nomenclature adopted is "NAP-MYL-01" and "NAP-MYL-02"; two were impregnated with the adhesion-inhibiting liquid, according to the LAI technique, and afterwards wrapped by CFRP, they will be referred to as "NAP-LIQ-01" and "NAP-LIQ-02". Finally, two specimens were left unconfined, so as to be taken as reference specimens for comparison of results (referred to as "NAP-URM-01" and "NAP-URM-02"). The aforementioned NAP samples were built from 55x120x250 mm³ squared Neapolitan tuff blocks; lime-based mortar was used for the joints, which were about 10 mm thick. The resulting half-scale column had a height h of 600 mm, corresponding to nine courses of blocks, and a square cross-section with dimensions equal to 250x250 mm². Corners were rounded with a radius of curvature r_c equal to 20 mm to avoid "knife effects" due to stress concentration. Similarly, as for the 8 PL specimens, two were confined with CFRP by using common wet lay-up (here labeled "PL-FRP-01" and "PL-FRP-02"); two were first wrapped with a Mylar™ film, according to the ISF technique, and afterwards CFRP-confined as same as for the NAP series, for them, the nomenclature adopted is "PL-MYL-01" and "PL-MYL-02". Two were impregnated with the adhesion-inhibiting liquid, according to the LAI technique, and afterwards CFRP-confined (here labelled as "PL-LIQ-01" and "PL-LIQ-02"). Finally, two reference columns were left unconfined, and labeled respectively as "PL-URM-01" and "PL-URM-02". The PL samples were built from squared limestone blocks of 55x120x250 mm³. The same lime-based mortar was used for the joints, which were about 10 mm thick. The resulting half-scale column had a height h of 660 mm, corresponding to ten courses of blocks, and a square cross-section with dimensions equal to 250x250 mm². The corners were rounded to ensure a radius of curvature r_c equal to 20 mm. Figure 1 shows the above dimensions and stratigraphies of the various types of reinforcement adopted for the case of PL specimens. In all cases the direction of the confining fibres was at 90° respect to the principal axis of the columns. Figure 1 summarizes in schematic form the characteristics of the specimens listed above.

Materials properties and test set-up

The dry carbon fiber sheets used as reinforcement had an equivalent thickness of 0.056 mm, with a mass density of 1.8 g/cm³. The mechanical properties of the unidirectional CFRP composite used for confinement were obtained through experimental characterization of 5 specimens subjected to tensile testing according to ASTM D7565/D7565M. The results showed linear elastic behaviour up to failure

of the composite, with an average elastic modulus of 334.98 GPa and an average tensile strength value of 2021.50 MPa, with coefficients of variations all less than 10%. The column specimens were all tested under uniaxial compression within a closed, rigid steel frame. A square steel plate 30 mm thick was placed at the top and base of the specimen, and two additional smaller steel plates 25 mm thick were placed on top of the specimen in the loaded region. The load was applied by means of a 250 ton hydraulic jack, which reacts against the aforementioned steel frame and is operated by means of a manual hydraulic pump. In all tests, two displacement transducers (LVDTs) with a capacity of 100 mm were used to measure the shortening of the column under the loading stages. The two LVDTs were placed at opposite corners of the steel plate at the top of the specimen, and the results were averaged, so as to measure the displacements and to account for possible effects due to accidental eccentricities. The load was controlled and measured by means of a load cell having a capacity of 30 ton. The applied load and axial displacements were recorded in real time by an electronic data acquisition system. All tests were conducted under the same temperature and humidity conditions ($T=21^{\circ}\text{C}$; R.H.=40-50%), reproducing the same procedural steps repetitively, so as to minimize data acquisition errors and effects related to different thermo-hygrometric conditions. Figure 2 shows a photo of a sample within the test machine described above accompanied by a schematic representation of the test setup and the "top view" detail related to the positioning of the LVDTs.

Figure 1: Experimental programme and specimen configurations (mm)

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the experimental results obtained from compression tests performed on NAP series and PL series specimens, both confined and unconfined. The unstrengthened columns were considered as reference specimens for determining the masonry properties with the aim of computing the contribution of the different confinement techniques in terms of stiffness, strength, displacement capacity and failure mode. The compression tests on specimens from the NAP-URM and PL-URM

series allowed to obtain the stress-strain curves shown in Figure 3 and representative of the mechanical behavior of unconfined masonry under axial loading.

Column specimen within the test frame

Schematic test set-up

Figure 2: Test set-up

As can be seen in Figure 3, the tests led to almost coincident results for the two masonry specimens of each repetition. For both series (NAP and PL), the specimens exhibited a typical brittle behavior, with sudden drop in strength at column crush. Pseudo-vertical cracks were formed during the loading phases and passed through both the mortar joints and the blocks, causing local disaggregation of the masonry in the final stages. In the case of the PL specimens, there was also a phenomenon of local expulsion of the masonry near the maximum load reached. The PL series specimens have shown higher stiffness and strength respect to the tuff masonry. This was expected since the mechanical properties of the limestone is typically higher than natural tuff.

Natural tuff masonry

Limestone masonry

Figure 3: Stress vs axial strain curves and failure modes of unconfined masonry

From the curves in Figure 4, the contribution of FRP-confinement is evident when compared with those illustrated in Figure 3 for unconfined masonry. An increase in strength is observed in all cases, as well as the presence of a post-peak branch, denoting a more ductile response of the columns when subjected to axial compression. For both specimens of each pair (NAP and PL), the results are comparable. The NAP-FRP-01 specimen exhibits a softening trend in the post peak branch, while in all the other cases a pseudo hardening trend is visible after the slope change of the curves which means the start of severe damage inside the masonry core. These differences are due to the brittle behaviour of masonry which is prone to irregular cracking progression. In all cases it is clear that the deformation capacity in terms of axial strain has been significantly improved by the presence of the FRP confinement, as expected by the theory and previous results in literature. In all cases the mechanical response of masonry columns remained higher respect to the tuff columns, As visible in

the pictures of Figure 4 the failure mode of the CFRP-confined columns was characterized by a lateral expansion of the core, with local ruptures of the fibres located in the corner regions, but without showing a catastrophic failure. The CFRP jacket remained bonded to the column as a "deformed bag" without showing a diffuse tensile failure of the fibres. The different post peak behaviour is due to the different damage progression of the brittle masonry core, as observed later for limestone columns too.

Figure 4: Stress vs axial strain curves and failure modes of FRP-masonry with wet lay-up technique

Compression tests performed on the NAP and PL columns confined with the LAI technique returned the curves shown in Figure 5 on the left for the tuff columns, and on the right for the stone columns, respectively. From observing the trend of the curves and reading the values of engineering interest such as maximum load, ultimate strain and load at slope change, no significant differences can be discerned compared to the specimens confined with the "traditional" wet lay-up (Fig. 4). The failure modes in terms of ULS were not different from the respective NAP/PL FRP series, local failure of the fibres was observed along the corners, with widespread swelling of the confined core suggesting severe damage to the masonry inside.

Figure 5: Stress vs axial strain curves and failure modes of FRP-masonry with LAI technique

The results of the compression tests performed on the NAP and PL columns confined with the ISF are represented in terms of stress vs strain curves in Figure 6 on the left for the tuff columns, and on the right for the stone columns, respectively. Also in this case of masonry columns confined by debonded FRP jacket, the trend of the curves and the values of engineering interest reveal that there are no significant differences in the mechanical response, if compared to the columns confined with the "traditional" wet lay-up (Fig. 4). The failure modes in terms of ULS were not different from the respective NAP/PL FRP series, local failure of the fibres was observed along the corners, with widespread swelling of the confined core suggesting severe damage to the masonry inside.

After the execution of the compression tests the CFRP jacket was removed from each specimen by making a sharp vertical cut without producing vibration or mechanical shocks to the specimens. This allowed to assess first the degree of removability of the FRP strengthening systems according to the different installation techniques and then, the level of reversibility of the applied confinement.

Starting with the FRP series specimens, characterized by a pure chemical bond between the surface

and the FRP system, the removal of the jacket led to the results depicted in Figure 7, for the NAP and PL specimens. As can be seen from the Figure 7, when the FRP jacket is classically applied to the masonry by the manual wet lay-up technique, it is not possible to remove it.

Figure 6: Stress vs axial strain curves and failure modes of FRP-masonry with ISF technique

The removal was difficult and resulted in the destruction of the specimen, since the resin, having permeated within the substrate, remained bonded to it, causing a cohesive spalling of the masonry. Detachment occurred diffusely at the level of the masonry substrate for both NAP and PL masonry. From the pictures very deep portions of the substrate that remained attached to the CFRP jacket are evident, causing severe alteration of the column. As expected, the wet lay-up technique cannot be considered removable.

Figure 7: Removability of the FRP confinement: NAP-FRP (top), PL-FRP (down) specimens

In the case of the LAI technique, the application of an adhesion-inhibiting liquid prior to the application of the FRP sheets allowed easy removal of the jacket. Therefore, the reinforcement appears to be mechanically removable but not extensively in terms of architectural preservation. Figure 8 illustrates the state of preservation of the columns inside and the involvement of the masonry cortical layer in the removal phase of the FRP system.

Even if the results in terms of removability improved respect to the case of the wet lay-up, observations of the removed jackets revealed significant portions of the substrate bound to them, which resulted in alteration at the surface level, especially for the NAP columns series. In the case of PL specimens the portions of the substrate that remain attached to the jacket were minimal and somewhat superficial. Thus the alteration of the surface was minimal in terms of detachment, but a chromatic change was evidenced. This was due to the type of release agent used. The differences in terms of adhesion between the two substrates can be attributable to the greater porosity of the Neapolitan

tuff compared to the limestone, which is related to the low viscosity of the adhesion-inhibiting liquid used. After all the LAI technique can be considered moderately reversible for compact stone masonry and not reversible for masonry built with porous blocks. In presence of frescos and decoration paintings this technique was not found to be compatible with the needs of removability.

Figure 8: Removability of the FRP confinement (LAI): NAP-LIQ (top), PL-LIQ (down) specimens

Finally, as for the MYL series specimens (see Figure 9), it was possible to remove very easily the CFRP jacket entirely, without appreciating any mechanical or chromatic alteration of the specimens, as can be seen from the pictures, relating to both NAP and PL specimens. As can be seen from the photos, by coating the columns with Mylar™ sheets prior to resin application, the CFRP jacket produced a non-adhesive envelope that can be easily and entirely removed without changing the aspect of the surface all along the column. In this way the substrate remained isolated and did not suffer any aesthetic or physical alteration. It follows that the ISF reinforcement technique is not only fully removable but also fully reversible, as it allows the reinforcement to be removed without leaving any traces, and allowing a new ISF-jacketing, if necessary.

Figure 9: Removability of the FRP confinement (ISF): NAP-MYL (top), PL-MYL (down) specimens

The results recorded during compression tests on the tested were evaluated in relation to their ability to produce an effective mechanical upgrade of the columns, as expected by the confinement effect. This effectiveness was quantified in terms of both strength and ductility of the confined specimens in comparison with the average values of the characteristics of the reference specimens (i.e.,

unconfined). The results of this comparison are shown in Table 1 for the NAP specimens and Table 2 for the PL specimens, in which:

- f_{cm}^m is the average value of the compressive strength for the columns confined with CFRP
- f_m^m is the average value of the compressive strength for the unconfined masonry columns
- ε_{cc}^m is the average value of the ultimate axial strain recorded for the columns confined with CFRP
- ε_{co}^m is the average value of the ultimate axial strain recorded for the unconfined masonry columns

As can be seen from the tables, the values of the ratio of confined to unconfined average strength values were obtained were 1.25, 1.39 and 1.54, for Neapolitan tuff, while 1.11, 1.33 and 1.37, for limestone. It follows that confinement was effective, in terms of strength, in both cases and regardless of the reinforcement application technique. The lower mechanical properties of the tuff respect to the limestone have promoted more efficient confinement as expected from the theory. It is shown by the results that the CFRP-confinement offers a relevant contribution in terms of strength in the case of the NAP specimens, where an increase in strength of up to 64 percent was obtained for the NAP-FRP-01 specimen. The least contribution resulted from the confinement of sample PL-LIQ-02, which exhibited strength values comparable to those of the unconfined reference specimen. This appears to be attributable to an initial local compressive failure that was observed at one corner, probably due to an unintended eccentricity of the axial load.

Table 1: Experimental results NAP Series

Specimen	Compressive strength f (MPa)			Ultimate axial strain ε_u (%)			Strength increase f_{cm}^m/f_m^m	Displacem. increase $\varepsilon_{cc}^m/\varepsilon_{co}^m$
	single test	mean	COV %	single test	mean	COV %		
NAP-URM-01	2.32	2.24	5.38	0.44	0.49	13.12	-	-
NAP-URM-02	2.15			0.53				
NAP-FRP-01	3.67	3.43	9.90	0.89	1.07	23.79	1.54	2.18
NAP-FRP-02	3.19			1.25				
NAP-LIQ-01	2.95	2.79	8.11	1.05	1.02	4.88	1.25	2.08
NAP-LIQ-02	2.63			0.98				
NAP-MYL-01	3.29	3.10	8.67	1.41	1.19	26.11	1.39	2.43
NAP-MYL-02	2.91			0.97				

Table 2: Experimental results PL Series

Specimen	Compressive strength f (MPa)			Ultimate axial strain ε_u (%)			Strength increase f_{cm}^m/f_m^m	Strain increase $\varepsilon_{cc}^m/\varepsilon_{co}^m$
	single test	mean	COV %	single test	mean	COV %		
PL-URM-01	4.21	4.10	3.97	0.33	0.33	0.00	-	-
PL-URM-02	3.98			0.33				
PL-FRP-01	5.05	5.43	9.90	0.97	1.11	17.28	1.33	3.35
PL-FRP-02	5.81			1.24				
PL-LIQ-01	4.71	4.55	5.13	0.51	0.64	28.73	1.11	1.94
PL-LIQ-02	4.38			0.77				
PL-MYL-01	6.14	5.63	12.95	1.17	1.04	18.45	1.37	3.14
PL-MYL-02	5.11			0.90				

From Tables 1 and 2, the ductility contribution offered by confinement can be quantified. For NAP specimens, the ratio of confined over unconfined ultimate axial strain varies between 2.08 to 2.43, while for PL specimens it varies between 1.94 and 3.35, where the lower value is referred to the specimen PL-LIQ-01 which has been previously discussed. In all cases this strain ratio is greater than unity, evidencing an increase in ductility of the specimen offered by confinement and more importantly it resulted independent from the CFRP application technique. Those specimens that have shown a pseudo-softening behaviour after the reach of the unconfined strength (knee point of the stress vs axial strain curve), have returned lower values of the ultimate axial strain. In those cases where the confining action produced a pseudo hardening branch after the knee point of the stress vs

strain curves, the displacement capacity of the columns increased, as testified by the values of the ultimate axial strain recorded during the tests.

Normalizing the axial stress and strain values measured during the tests conducted on the FRP, LIQ and MYL series by the averaged values of the maxima relative to the ultimate strength and ultimate strain of the URM series the diagrams shown in Figure 10 are obtained, respectively, for the NAP and PL specimens. On the vertical axis there is the ratio f_{cm}/f_m where the symbols are those recalled above. This expresses the effectiveness of confinement in terms of increased load bearing capacity. On the horizontal axis there is the ratio μ_{cm}/μ_m where:

$$\mu = (\varepsilon_u - \varepsilon_p) / \varepsilon_p \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

is the ductility index with:

ε_u is the ultimate axial strain recorded in the tests

ε_p is the axial strain in correspondence of the end of the first pseudo linear branch

μ_m is the ductility index referred to unconfined plain masonry

μ_{cm} is the ductility index referred to FRP-confined masonry

This ratio expresses the effectiveness of FRP-confinement in terms of deformation capacity, which identifies the ductility of the system as a strain energy retention factor.

From the diagrams it is easy to quantify the effectiveness of CFRP confinement in terms of both ductility and strength, and how this effectiveness is independent from the installation technique applied (wet lay-app, LAI or ISF).

Figure 10: Normalized curves for NAP (top) and PL (bottom) specimens

In order to testify the effectiveness of the confinement in the case of ISF CFRP-confined columns, where the reversibility was found to be complete, a picture of the failed cross section is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Example of failed ISF CFRP-confined column specimen

It is visible from the different damage levels along the area of the cross section that the lateral pressure generated by the confinement followed the theoretical prediction. The maximum effectiveness appears to be found in correspondence of the corners and in the core region, while the external areas far from the corner were cracked and spalled after the FRP removal. This testifies the presence of an ineffective region due to the prismatic shape of the cross section. In this region the multiaxial stress state cannot be reached, due to geometric limitations, therefore the properties are those of unconfined masonry. As important results it demonstrated, from a mechanical perspective, that even in total absence of bond between the FRP sheets and the masonry column, the confinement acts without any significant difference respect to the case of fully bonded jacket.

CONCLUSIONS

The research presented herein allowed to study the reversibility of new strengthening techniques for the FRP-confinement of historical masonry columns, also in those cases where the high architectural value would discourage the use of FRP materials. Two techniques labeled as LAI (Liquid Adhesion Inhibitor) and the ISF (Interposition of a Separating Film) techniques were proposed and investigated in laboratory. The first is able to prevent the impregnation of the masonry by the primer and the adhesive, thanks to the application of a liquid that prevent the adhesion with a physical function of release agent. The second technique allows to separate the masonry substrate from the external reinforcement, which is able to wrap the column without being in contact with it. In this case, Mylar™ sheets were used as separating film. The experimental tests involved sixteen specimens in the form of half-scale columns made by blocks of limestone and blocks of Neapolitan tuff. Centered compression tests were performed in order to evaluate the effectiveness of confinement for each of the solutions adopted. From the experimental results it was clear that FRP-confinement is effective both in terms of increasing strength and ductility, regardless of the solution adopted for the application of the reinforcement, even without any bonded region. After the tests, it was possible to remove the CFRP jackets from the specimens and to evaluate the removability of each installation technique that was used in this research. The results related to the new proposed techniques resulted strongly encouraging from a mechanical and architectural perspective since the effectiveness of confinement did not depend upon the installation techniques. From the observations after testing the LAI technique revealed to be a partially removable procedure, while ISF technique demonstrated to be fully removable and reversible. The LAI technique is recommended where the stone is not highly porous, since if the liquid penetrates inside the masonry skin it does not produce a sort of barrier for the epoxy primer and adhesive. In conclusion, if the LAI technique is a promising procedure in the perspective to promote removable and reversible confinement interventions for historical masonry columns with the, the ISF technique, following the experimental campaign conducted herein, is ready to be applied in the field, also for painted and decorated columns. In this case, the confinement has been demonstrated to be effective, removable and fully reversible.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.